

A New Ecosystem of Early Music Studies

COST ACTION CA21161

STSM-2025: Exploring AI-Assisted Techniques for Importing and Querying RISM Data

RISM Digital Center, University of Bern, 12 to 16 May 2025

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Introduction

This report is the outcome of experiments regarding the applications of artificial intelligence (AI) and other technologies to the database of the *Répertoire International des Sources Musicales* (RISM), conducted as part of the Short-Term Scientific Mission (STSM), which was financed by the EarlyMuse Cost Action, and took place at the RISM Digital Center in Bern, Switzerland, from 12 to 16 May 2025. The experiments were conducted along four principal axes:

1. Importing missing data into RISM using AI,
2. Visualizing RISM data,
3. SPARQL query development,
4. MiniMUSCAT

1. Importing missing data into RISM using AI

The first task of the STSM focused on filling gaps within RISM Online capabilities. The 2024 RISM STSM focused on identifying these gaps, focusing on the Howard Mayer Brown catalogues as well as some of the RISM *series* catalogues (e.g., B/I-II [printed

collections], B/VI [treatises], B/VII [notated manuscript lute music sources]). Due to the minimal gaps in the Brown data, it was concluded that the best solution for this particular catalogue was to enter the data by hand, to take place at a later date. However, it was decided that for the complete RISM *series* missing from RISM Online, adopting a machine-based approach was most efficient. This year's RISM Online STSM sought to test new machine learning technology (e.g., FormAI) to see if it was possible to speed up this process while maintaining accuracy. We tested machine learning tools (colloquially known as AI) to see if it would be possible to extract information from PDF scans of the hard-copy RISM series catalogues, encode it, and add it to the RISM *Online* database.

Extracting information in this context refers to two distinguishable aspects:

1. Extracting the text
2. Extracting the text structure

While extracting text is possible with standard OCR technology, the main difficulty for extracting the information from a publication such as the RISM *series* catalogues is extracting the structure of the information. The structure of hard-copy RISM catalogues is unique to music inventories, meaning that AI tools are often not trained to handle this kind of metadata. The OCR capabilities of most tools are often not inherently suitable for RISM catalogues, as the said catalogues often feature a wide range of languages and specialist abbreviations.

Extracting data from RISM B/VI/1 and B/VI/2 (music treatises)

Trial 1: Encode from PDF without OCR (unsuccessful)

The first trial attempted to encode the information directly from the PDF without a separate initial OCR step, using ChatGPT. It was unsuccessful, as the information in JSON code was incomplete and unclear.

Trial 2: Use OCR and AI tool to encode (unsuccessful)

This trial attempted to use OCR on the PDF using different tools like OCR4all, ABBYY FineReader and *onlineocr* to find the most reliable in extracting the text into a txt plain format. After trying a number of tools, our preference was for *onlineocr* because it was faster, free and most accessible. In this instance it also resulted in the cleanest visual appearance. From here in txt plain format, we uploaded it to different AI Tools such as ChatGPT, Gemini, NotebookLM and FormX.ai. The JSON obtained from these tools was scrambled for some of the fields including the libraries' siglum and variation of languages in the document, thus still not creating a successful end product.

The OCR process for this copy was particularly problematic as, firstly, the catalogue includes a serious mix of languages, e.g. English, Italian, French, etc., as illustrated in

the following example. Secondly, the abbreviations used both for the format of the publication, as well as the library sigla donating where the copies are kept, might not be easy to detect. Furthermore, the OCR resulting text does not keep the structure of the text which can cause more problems with accuracy.

Figure: Page 521 of RISM B VI illustrating the mixture of different languages in the treatise.

Example of data extraction on a composer by ChatGPT:

ADAN (Don Vicente)

Documentos para instruccion de musicos, y aficionados, que intentan saber el arte de la composicion. En esta obra se trata de los contrapuntos sobre bajo hasta siete, sobre tiple hasta siete, y suelto hasta ocho, y dos exemplos á doce voces, todas en fuga unas con otras . . . Compuesta y ordenada por Don Vicente Adan. – *Madrid, Joseph Otero, 1786. In-4, 15–75 p.*

D G

Figure: Sample card from RISM B VI.

Avan (Don Vicente) Documentos para instruccion de musicos, y aficionados, que intentan saber el arte de la composicion... – Madrid, Joseph Otero, 1786. In-4, 15-75 p.

```
{
  "composer": "Avan (Don Vicente).",
  "title": "Documentos para instruccion de musicos, y aficionados, que intentan saber el arte de la composicion... "
  "printer": "[Contre J. A. P. Schulz] – Madrid, Joseph Otero ",
  "year": "1786",
  "format": "In-4",
  "pages": "15-75 p.",
  "libraries": [""]
}
```

We chose these fields (composer, title, printer, year, format, pages, libraries) to remain consistent with the entries within RISM Online for the other catalogues. However, as can be seen by the example above, there were some issues with text recognition (Adan/Avan) as well as more specific layout issues.

Trial 3: Encode using FormX.ai

We uploaded the unprocessed PDF directly to FormX.ai to structure and encode the information. It was possible to extract the information but not all the entries on each page were detected, the extractor only processing one entry per page. For this reason, we decided to try to use this tool again but processing first the PDF to facilitate the extraction of all the information.

Trial 4: Using Cards to extract the information in FormX.ai

Due to the layout and extraction issues, we realised it was required to isolate certain information as a 'card'. We decided to frame the information related only to one entry (one source) from a page, and to train FormX.ai to extract relevant information, restructuring it into MARCXML. We understood that the names of composers caused some confusion for the *ai* because of the layout (the composer's name appeared separately above the main body text). Moreover, as in text-structured bibliographies, the composer/author's name is not repeated for each of his works, and a hyphen is used in its place. We then had to train the language learning model to repeat the former composers' names in this instance.

We used ChatGPT to extract independently the name of the composer and the card for each entry of the PDF, and at the same time associate both outputs of information. The script also allows for the previous composers' name to be inserted when a hyphen appears.

AIGUINO ALBARET

AIGUINO (Illuminato) da Brescia

La Illuminata de tutti i tuoni di canto fermo, con alcuni bellissimi secreti non d'altrui piu scritti, composta per il Reverendo Padre Frate Illuminato Aiguino da Bressa, dell'ordine seraphico d'Osservanza. – Venezia, Antonio Gardano, 1562. In-8, 58 f.

B Br – BR Rem – D B; GOI – F Pc; Pn – GB Ge; Lbm (2 ex.); T – I AN; Be; LA; Me; Ria; RE m; Vnm; Vlb – US AAu; Cn; NYp; R; Wcm – YU Dgmb

Il tesoro illuminato di tutti i tuoni di canto figurato, con alcuni bellissimi secreti, non da altri più scritti: nuovamente composto dal Reverendo Padre Frate Illuminato Aiguino bresciano, dell'ordine serafico d'osservanza. – Venezia, Giovanni Varisco, 1581. In-8, 88 f.

A Wn – B Br – D B; Hs; MÜs; Rp – F Pa; Pc; Pm; Pn (2 ex.) – GB Ge; Lbm (2 ex.); Lcm – I A; Bc; BGe; Fc; LA; Mb; Nc (2 ex.); Rc; Rli; Rsc (2 ex.); Tn; Vnm – NL DHgm – US Cn; LEX; NYp; R; SFsc; Wcm

AIKIN (John)

Essays on song-writing; with a collection of such English songs as are most eminent for poetical merit. To which are added some original pieces. – London, Joseph Johnson, [1772]. In-8, 280 p.

C Tu – GB Cu; Lbm – US CH-H

— The second edition with additions and corrections. Warrington, W. Eyres for Joseph Johnson, 1774. In-8, 286 p.

F Pn (2 ex.) – GB Ckc; Cu; Lbm (2 ex.) – US CH-H; Clu; R (2 ex.); Wc

— Dublin, 1777.

GB Ge

ALANDER (Christiernus) Voir PREUTZ (Samuel)

ALARD (Lambert)

Lamp. Alardi . . . de veterum musica liber singularis: in fine accessit Paelli sapientissimi musica à Graeco in latinum sermonem translata, autore eodem. – Schleusingen, Peter Faber (Henning Gross), 1636. In-8, 203 p.

A Wgm; Wn; Wu – B Be – CS Pnm – D B; Bds; Bim; BM; DI; ERu; G; Lr; LEm (2 ex.); LÜh; Mbs; Rp; W; WR – DK Kk – F Pc; Pm (2 ex.); Pn; Psg; Sn – GB Ge; Lbm (2 ex.); Ob (2 ex.) – I Mb; Rsc; Rvat; Vnm – PL WRo – S Skma – US BE; Cn; Cu; NYp; Wcm

ALBARET (d') Voir Lettre familière de M. le comte d'Albaret . . .

74

Figure: Example of the layout of the page 74 of RISM B VI with the frame created. Composers' names are selected in green and the rest of the content is selected in red.

The screenshot shows the FormX.ai interface for training a custom model. The sidebar on the left contains navigation links: Extractors, Add-ons, Workspaces (with a 'New' button), Detect Documents, Help Center, API Doc, Contact Us, Team, Manage Team, Usage, and Plans & Billing. The main content area is titled 'Extractors > Custom Model' and includes tabs for 'Data Fields', 'Training Samples', 'Test Extractor', 'API', and 'Settings'. Under 'Training Samples', there is a sub-header 'Training Samples' and a description: 'Provide us with sample files, this helps with the extraction performance.' There are buttons for 'Delete Samples (0)' and 'Add Sample'. Three sample cards are displayed, each with a checkbox, a thumbnail of a document page, and a caption: 'card-01.jpg', 'card-02.jpg', and 'card-03.jpg', all with 'Reviewed' status and 'Uploaded at: 5/14/2025'.

Figure: Example of a training sample of three cards from RISM B VI in FormX.ai.

The nature, pleasure and advantages of church-musick. A sermon preached at a lecture in the first parish of Lancaster, on thursday april 4th. 1771. By Zabdiel Adams . . . – Boston, Richard Draper, 1771. In-8, 38 p. US Bel; Bhh; Bhs; CAc; Hm; NYcu; NYp; PROc; Wcm; WOa

Reviewed Sample
FormX will use the testing image and results to enhance the performance

composer	• Zabdiel ADAMS
title	• The nature, pleasure and advantages of church- musick. A sermon preached at a lecture in the first parish of Lancaster, on thursday april 4th. 1771.
printer	• Richard Draper
year	• 1771
format	• In- 8
pages	• 38
libraries	• US Bel; US Bhh; US Bhs; US CAc; Hm; US NYcu; US NYp; US PROc; US Wcm; US WOa

Figure: Example of how FormX.ai extracted the information from the sample card shown above.

Although we are relatively happy with this process, the main inconvenience of using FormX.ai is that it can only process one card at a time - It is not designed to be able to process a large amount of information at the same time.

The next steps involve evaluating the card extraction ratio, improving the accuracy of page break splits, and converting the extracted data into minimal MARCXML format. A key issue to address is ensuring that each library siglum includes the appropriate country code, as this is not repeated in the siglum list, and mapping the complete sigla with the corresponding RISM ID. Additionally, composer names need to be reconciled with RISM person authorities. Once all the data is clearly extracted and properly encoded, it will be inserted into Muscat.

2. Visualizing RISM data

General considerations

Large databases or datasets with complex underlying data models are often difficult to grasp in their entirety, especially without extensive dedicated training. When engaging with RISM, one can feel overwhelmed with not only the number of records available and accessible, but also with the interrelations between different types of data and the relations between them. In many areas of academic activity, data visualization is employed as an aid to visually represent (aspects of) such large and complex data, which sometimes may even lead to unexpected discoveries that were not apparent or escaped one's attention when querying the data.

At the same time, data visualization faces serious limitations that one should be aware of. For example, we can only represent two- or three-dimensional images on computer screens (or paper, for that matter), which normally is orders of magnitudes smaller than the actual shape of the data. Data visualization is thus not simply a mapping from data to screen: it crucially involves taking decisions of *what* is being visualized *how*. It commonly entails reducing complex data to simpler representations using projections, dimensionality reduction, or other techniques, and thus requires some data-analytical experience as well as a solid sense for aesthetics: data visualization can reveal but also hide information!

During the course of this STSM, one goal was to graphically show relations between different types of RISM records as a case study that can later be altered in order to show other perspectives. RISM Online¹ provides an excellent way of exploring the RISM catalog, mainly through textual search and a number of useful toggle switches, thus allowing users to obtain an intuitive understanding of its underlying data model—or simply to find entries one had been looking for.

Accessing the data

Each entry in RISM that is retrievable through RISM Online has, at the bottom of the page, a persistent URI that makes it identifiable and potentially allows for matching with other databases (musicological or other). Moreover, these URIs are both human- and machine-readable. For instance, the link <https://rism.online/sources/1001256949> reveals that it is a link to a "source" with ID 1001256949. Following the link in a web browser leads to a page that contains information about that source's title and content

¹ <https://rism.online/>

description, the material description, references and further notes, locations of exemplars, as well as relations to other sources. The figure below shows a screenshot for this entry. Note that this information is partially optional so that not every source has the same kinds of entries.

Choros-E minor; Print; AppV W161

Description

Title and content description

Composer/Author	Villa-Lobos, Heitor (1887-1957) [Ascertained]
Source type	Print
Content type	Notated music
Dates	ca. 1950-1960
Key or mode	E minor
Standardized title	Choros
Title on source	[caption title:] Chôros (N o 1) (typico) H. Villa-Lobos
Additional title	Chôros Nr. 1
Scoring summary	guit
Total scoring	guit (1)
RISM ID number	sources/1001256949
Subject headings	Instrumental pieces

Material description

Group 01

Source type: Print

Record URI (Permalink): <https://rism.online/sources/1001256949>
 API Viewer: [JSON-LD](#) [MARCXML](#) | [Report an issue](#)

Figure: Screenshot of the record for URI <https://rism.online/sources/1001256949> in RISM Online.

Below the persistent URI, one finds links to the representation of the same data in two different machine-readable formats: JSON-LD (JSON Linked Data) and MARCXML (see the figure below). Clicking on one of those will open the API Viewer where one can switch between different data representations (some still experimental).

Record URI: <https://rism.online/sources/1001256949>

```

1  {
2    "@context": "https://rism.online/api/v1/source.json",
3    "id": "https://rism.online/sources/1001256949",
4    "type": "rism:Source",
5    "typeLabel": {
6      "de": [
7        "Quelle"
8      ],
9      "en": [
10       "Source"
11     ],
12     "es": [
13       "Fuente"
14     ],
15     "fr": [
16       "Source"

```

API Format

- JSON-LD
- MARCXML
- Turtle (experimental)
- N-triples (experimental)

Response Languages

- All languages
- Selected languages

API Request

```
curl -XGET -H "Accept: application/ld+json" https://rism.online/sources/1001256949
```

Figure: API Viewer of the record <https://rism.online/sources/1001256949>.

The API request is displayed at the bottom right so that one can pull this information locally using a standard terminal. This provides a convenient interface to query and access the data and work with it locally. The figure below shows how the API request provided in the API Viewer can be used to retrieve a full record in MARCXML.

```

$ curl -XGET -H "Accept: application/marcxml+xml" https://rism.online/sources/1001256949
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
<record xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance" xmlns="http://www.loc.gov/MARC21/slim" xsi:schemaLocation="http://www.loc.gov/standards/marcxml/schema/MARC21slim.xsd">
  <leader>00000ncm a2200000 u 4500</leader>
  <controlfield tag="001">sources/1001256949</controlfield>
  <controlfield tag="003">DE-633</controlfield>
  <controlfield tag="005">20250305101418.0</controlfield>
  <datafield tag="035" ind1=" " ind2=" ">
    <subfield code="a">456023813</subfield>
    <subfield code="3">holdings/51075704</subfield>
  </datafield>
  <datafield tag="040" ind1=" " ind2=" ">
    <subfield code="a">DE-633</subfield>
  </datafield>
  <datafield tag="100" ind1="1" ind2=" " >
    <subfield code="a">Villa-Lobos, Heitor</subfield>
    <subfield code="d">1887-1957</subfield>
    <subfield code="j">Ascertained</subfield>
    <subfield code="0">people/4101266</subfield>
  </datafield>
</record>

```

Figure: Sending an API request via the terminal and receiving data about a specific RISM entry.

For the purpose of this exploration for data visualization, however, it was more convenient not to use API calls, but rather work with dumps of the database that are provided for different kinds of records at <https://rism.digital/exports/>:² persons, publications, institutions, and sources, encoded in MARCXML. Each type also comes in a legacy variety to ensure consistency with systems using an older ID scheme. However, new applications should not draw on these. Note also that the size of the provided compressed files varies greatly: while ‘publications’ barely take 3 MB of disk space, ‘sources’ take more than 8 GB when extracted. One should also note the licensing of that data. As stated on the page:

This data is made available under a [Creative Commons CC-BY 3.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/) license. You are free to download and modify the data. You must give credit to RISM when republishing the data, and you must not apply any further restrictions for others’ use and access of the data.

Working with the data

As the data is provided in MARCXML encoding, a convenient way to process it is drawing on the *pymarc* Python library (<https://pymarc.readthedocs.io/>). The library’s GitLab page (<https://gitlab.com/pymarc/pymarc>) explains how to read MARCXML data using *pymarc* in two different ways: 1) Reading and storing all the data in memory

² Accessed on May 16, 2025.

is possible with the `parse_xml_to_array` function, but if the data to be read is large, it will take a long time to read in and be processed. 2) An alternative would be to stream the data using the `map_xml` function, which can be used to continuously print out records stored in the file. However, when wanting to *do* something with the data except printing, or when only a part of the data is to be accessed (e.g. for prototyping), one needs to override `pymarc`'s XML handler with some custom code:

```
class MyHandler(XmlHandler):
    """Process only SAMPLE_SIZE portion of the file."""
    def __init__(self):
        super().__init__()
        self.records = []

    def process_record(self, record):
        self.records.append(record)
        if len(self.records) >= SAMPLE_SIZE:
            raise StopIteration(f"Collected {SAMPLE_SIZE} records.")
```

Then, if one initializes a handler as, one can pass it to `parse_xml` like so:

```
handler = MyHandler()
try:
    parse_xml(MYFILE, handler)
except StopIteration:
    pass
```

For relational structures such as the interlinked records of the RISM database, networks or graphs are suitable visualizations, where nodes correspond to items (record types in this case) and links between them correspond to some relation (in this case, containment). At the moment of writing, RISM Online has 1,583,468 sources, each associated with rich (meta)data. For processing and visualization, this may constitute a severe challenge. In order to explore visualization capabilities in this STSM, we limited ourselves to the first $N = 360,000$ sources in the dump to conform to processing and memory limitations on our laptop. All of those records were parsed, and the final result was visualized using the popular `networkx` Python library.³ The final network (see the figure below) shows which holding institutions (e.g. libraries) contain which types of documents. Obviously, many other graphs can be produced showing relations between different kinds of record features, but this simple relation already allows for some interesting observations: First, the most common document type in the (subsample of) RISM records are manuscript copies, whereas prints only constitute a

³ <https://networkx.org/documentation/stable/index.html>)

minor proportion. This is by no means to be taken as representative, since this result might be heavily influenced by the processing order—recall that we are only looking at the *first N* records. Another observation is that, using document types, we can distinguish several holding institution groups: those that contain only manuscript copies from those that have more varied holdings (regarding manuscript type).

Figure: Network visualization of the 360.000 records contained in the sources file showing that most libraries hold “Manuscript copies”, “Autograph manuscripts” and “Possible autograph manuscripts” (large red nodes). Prints, in this export, are surprisingly few.

A major challenge is to link or match records from different files (or different API calls) as well as with other, external databases, such as Wikidata. This is also a field where AI technologies might be helpful.

3. SPARQL query development:

One of the new features brought by RISM Online and the JSON-LD is the availability of the data as Linked-Data. The RISM Digital Center maintains a SPARQL endpoint (currently accessible for registered users only) that allows for querying and analyzing the data in a much more flexible way than with the user interface or the underlying search API. In addition to the flexibility of the querying possibilities, the strength of the Linked-data endpoint is also the fact that it allows for querying across dataset, such as Wikidata. This enables building queries with search parameters or search results on data fields not available in the RISM data but that is relevant for a particular search.

One of the main difficulties with the use of Linked-data is that it requires the underlying model of the data to be known, as well as the SPARQL syntax for building the syntax itself. This is another area where Large Language Models (LLM) can assist building queries. For the RISM database, in order to use an existing LLM that has not been trained on the RISM data model, it is necessary to provide it with some context. A simple way to do this is to provide sample records containing the fields that will be included in the search one wants to make. This can be done by simply providing the Turtle sample records, and then asking to write a query based on it. This could be as simple as "Please build a query that will tell me how many sources are on the genre 'motet' in all sources between 1500 and 1545."

Result from ChatGPT:

```
PREFIX dcterms: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/>
PREFIX rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>
PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
PREFIX rism: <https://rism.online/api/v1#>
PREFIX xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>

SELECT (COUNT(?source) AS ?motetCount)
WHERE {
    ?source a rism:Source ;
            rism:hasDates ?dateInfo ;
            rism:hasSubject ?subject .

    ?dateInfo rism:earliestDate ?earliest ;
             rism:latestDate ?latest .

    ?subject rdf:value ?genre .

    FILTER(xsd:integer(?earliest) <= 1545 && xsd:integer(?latest) >= 1500)
    FILTER(CONTAINS(LCASE(STR(?genre)), "motet"))
}
```

NOTES:

- This counts all sources where:
 - The *latest date is before or in 1545*, and
 - The *earliest date is after or in 1500* (so the date range overlaps with 1500-1545),
 - And the genre label *contains "motet"* (case-insensitive).
- You may need to adapt the `rdf:value` or `rdfs:label` depending on how genre terms like "Motets" are encoded (in your sample, it's under `rdf:value` for subjects).

Putting this into <https://linked.rism.io/>

The screenshot shows the RISM Online SPARQL query interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with "RISM" and links for "Index Information", "Backend Information", and "Shortcuts / Help". The main area contains a SPARQL query editor with the following code:

```

1 PREFIX dcterms: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/>
2 PREFIX rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>
3 PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
4 PREFIX rism: <https://rism.online/api/v1#>
5 PREFIX xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>
6
7 SELECT (COUNT(?source) AS ?motetCount)
8 WHERE {
9   ?source a rism:Source ;
10          rism:hasDates ?dateInfo ;
11          rism:hasSubject ?subject .
12
13   ?dateInfo rism:earliestDate ?earliest ;
14            rism:latestDate ?latest .
15
16   ?subject rdf:value ?genre .
17
18   FILTER(xsd:integer(?earliest) <= 1545 && xsd:integer(?latest) >= 1500)
19   FILTER(CONTAINS(LCASE(STR(?genre)), "motet"))
20 }

```

Below the query editor, there are buttons for "Execute", "Download", and "Share". To the right, there are buttons for "Format", "Clear cache", "Analysis", and "Examples". A dropdown menu shows "3. Context sensitive suggestions" and a checkbox for "Automatically add names to result".

The "Query results:" section shows the following information:

- 1 lines found
- 360ms in total
- 152ms for computation
- 208ms for resolving and sending

The results table has one column labeled "?motetCount" and one row with the value "814".

Figure: Example of how information is queried from RISM Online using SPARQL.

A number of queries were developed, and we are confident we can continue this operation with success.

4. MiniMUSCAT

How to import data and metadata into Muscat - as opposed to entering data and metadata directly - has been discussed since Muscat's creation in 2014/15. The benefits of having import capability would mean that unaffiliated users without training (and therefore without access to Muscat) could provide data otherwise inaccessible to Muscat contributors, and that contributors could easily check, edit, and publish in RISM Online. This would ensure a much larger swathe of information (including from sources in private collections, or collections difficult to access geographically) could be accessible via RISM Online users.

The challenges thus far with import capability have mainly concerned the structure, curation, and quality of data and metadata provided in the import document. Importing spreadsheets proved essentially infeasible. In spreadsheet form, the data has to be encoded perfectly to import correctly, which is difficult to proof and edit on a small scale, let alone a large scale. There is also no authority control. For instance, when inputting the Composer/Author name to a spreadsheet, the user enters a plaintext name. In Muscat, a name is an authority; the user either selects from names already extant in the database, or chooses to create a new authority to add to the database. If a spreadsheet is imported with a name entered in a way that is not yet in the database (e.g., a slightly different spelling, with dates added in this field, etc.), this field will be flagged on import, requiring the proofreading Muscat contributor to manually change all relevant records. This makes spreadsheet submissions by the general public infeasible, as it would cause far too much disruption to Muscat contributors' proofreading and editing workflow.

Our goal in this STSM was to explore ways that users can input data and metadata that is structured and curated in a way that is directly compatible with Muscat, without making it such that anyone, regardless of knowledge or training, can publish records directly into RISM Online without any quality checks, thus undermining the quality and reliability of RISM Online. We decided that the best approach to explore was a simplified version of Muscat with restricted publishing ability, called MiniMuscat. This would ensure that the data, metadata, and authorities provided by the user are structured and curated correctly (making quality-checks by Muscat contributors feasible), while ensuring these records were unpublished until a trained editor had checked the entries.

We based our approach on a 1-2-3 fundamental workflow pattern:

1. An unaffiliated user enters data and metadata into MiniMuscat templates that are restricted to 'unpublished' (this field can be set as an immutable value, i.e., unchangeable by the user).
2. A Muscat contributor edits and quality-checks the records created by the unaffiliated user.
3. The Muscat contributor publishes these records in RISM Online.

We then drafted specifications for the MiniMuscat templates based on what we believed to be our target users. These target users include (but are not limited to):

1. Performers with a specialism in early music
2. Non-professional early music instrumentalists/singers
3. Musicologists/Music theorists
4. Archivists and/or librarians

We decided that MiniMuscat was not going to be nearly as flexible or all-encompassing as Muscat, but rather, a simpler, more public-facing interface. When creating templates for the MiniMuscat editor interface, we reduced the number of blocks to a single block. The block features fields that provide the most essential and useful metadata for RISM Online users. Equally, the fields selected provide data that we anticipated users would be able to enter accurately and consistently, and that Muscat contributors could proofread and edit efficiently. At present, we have excluded composite volumes from the template list, as these volumes are very complicated to catalogue, and we currently think that these are unlikely to be catalogued by our target users. We also established that MiniMuscat would be publically accessible using an automatically generated username and password with two-step verification, to ensure accessibility with security.

Having established the structure and fields featured, we made a test MiniMuscat editor for notated manuscript collection records, and accompanying test guidelines for entering data and metadata. We tested the editor on one of the STSM 3 grantees who had not yet interacted with Muscat. The test was mostly successful, with some necessary changes and clarification in the tutorial text identified and rectified.

One main structural challenge moving forward for building MiniMuscat is how users would create new authorities, mainly for personal names and places. We anticipate users needing to provide new names and places, as new information and new individuals are discovered in historical sources. There is substantial capacity for an integrated MiniMuscat editor resulting in Muscat being filled with authorities that are either redundant or incorrect. This would result in the Muscat contributors proofreading and editing the user-provided records not only to notice these

redundancies or inaccuracies and rectify this in said records, but to identify these authorities in Muscat and delete them. This would significantly decrease editorial efficiency and create more tombstone records in the database. Equally, it would severely disrupt the workflow of current Muscat contributors.

There are different potential approaches to this challenge. One approach that would address the latter issue in particular (i.e., workflow of current Muscat contributors) would be to find a way to separate Muscat and MiniMuscat, such that authorities entered in MiniMuscat did not appear in Muscat until the records were checked and published. This would ensure Muscat contributors continued to work with carefully controlled and monitored authorities. Another approach (possibly in addition to separating Muscat and MiniMuscat) would be to provide a standardised entry for fields in which we anticipate users providing new authorities, namely:

- Composer/Author (100)
- Standardised title (240\$a)
- Additional institution fields (710\$a) and (710\$c)
- Related place (551) in the personal name authority (or indeed, adding a place authority directly).

The user could then provide the metadata for this authority in the 'general notes' box. The Muscat contributors proofreading and editing user-provided records could filter by this standardised entry (e.g., 'New authority') to identify instances and add the authorities themselves. However, this would add to the already pressed time Muscat contributors have to proof-read and edit records. Equally, it may not be necessary; if we can separately store authorities added to MiniMuscat from authorities added to Muscat, there would be no risk of severe disruption to Muscat contributors' workflow, and we could safely test to see whether target users were prone to mis-entering authorities.

Another major question is whether MiniMuscat would provide adequate return on investment of time and resources. At present, the number of trained Muscat contributors who regularly enter, proofread, and edit data/meta-data/authorities entered into Muscat would not be adequate to handle the increase in record entries we would need to justify the investment required to create MiniMuscat. As such, it would be necessary to ensure there were enough Muscat contributors with capacity to act as proof-readers and editors for MiniMuscat entries to justify MiniMuscat's creation. While this would comprise an additional investment, we predict such an investment would provide significant returns that would continue to grow well beyond MiniMuscat. The most obvious returns are that there would be more trained contributors entering and cleaning data in Muscat, as well as more awareness of RISM-Online among its target users. Endeavours to increase the number of trained

contributors to Muscat in conjunction with developing MiniMuscat would also have wider benefits for education and outreach. One approach would be to start up some group training workshops for institutions and organisations, including (but not limited to):

- 'Amateur' early music societies (e.g., the English Folk Dance and Song Society, Collegium Musicum Costa del Sol, etc.)
- Archives
- Parish churches and Cathedrals
- University libraries
- Municipal libraries
- Civic record offices
- Further education institutions (e.g., training undergraduates and having them do work in Muscat for course credit)

Such training workshops have already been tested in the form of week-long work placements for sixth-form students via the AHRC-funded 'Music, Heritage, Place' project (a collaboration between Royal Holloway University of London and Newcastle University). These placements have shown that young people are not only highly capable of doing such work, but have a keen interest in this form of music history research. The students expressed a desire to continue doing voluntary inventory work for Muscat. Running such workshops in further and/or higher educational institutions would also increase awareness of music history and its place in the wider digital humanities among young people, and provide important work experience from a data science perspective. This would also help with upskilling librarians and archivists to enable more music cataloguing, something various organisations - including the International Association of Music Libraries, Archives and Documentation Centres (IAML) - have noted as a desirable wider objective.

This idea is very much in its infancy and requires further discussion with RISM Editorial Center office in Frankfurt. There are many details to be discussed and structures to assess. However, it is clear that there could very well be a workable solution for crowd-sourcing cataloguing endeavours in a way that ensures RISM Online continues to provide high-quality, reliable information for its users. The question that remains is whether it would be worth the investment of time and resources to create MiniMuscat at present.

Conclusions

Lessons learned during the STSM

- There are multiple steps required for data extraction (there is no one quick solution). Workflows must be divided into structured steps in order to be viable; it is not possible to do everything in a single step if an accurate result is desired.
- Given that developing or training an automated system remains time-consuming, manual cataloging often proves to be both faster and more efficient, especially for shorter documents.
- There are many technological tools available for carrying out a variety of tasks that can be leveraged for music-related projects. Existing tools can be adapted to the specific needs of a project, avoiding the need to develop something from scratch.
- When extracting data from RISM Online using SPARQL, it has been observed that the amount of information available in databases depends both on the resources allocated to research by the institutions from a given location and on the specific interests of the researchers who contribute data to RISM Online. As a result, not all information is equally represented, and significant gaps still remain.
- It is important to ensure that data is shareable and reusable to enhance sustainability for various purposes and across different databases, so that projects have a better chance of long-term survival and lasting impact.
- Equipment limitations when moving from prototype to larger datasets - (performance, scalability, security issues)

Follow-up activities planned

- MiniMuscat to be used to input basic data by supplementary users on projects such as the Music, Heritage, Place project (Royal Holloway University of London and Newcastle University).
- These experiments have shown the feasibility to commence data extraction from RISM *series* catalogues. Resources required to commence with B/VI [treatises]

- Enter missing Howard Mayer Brown entries via updating spreadsheet and input via Muscat to RISM Online.
- Investigate the option of creating a chatbot so that SPARQL queries are created in the background once a question is asked, and the query outcome is provided directly.